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Evaluating Ergonomic Risk for Nurses During Patient Transfers: A Pilot Study

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KEYWORDS

Nurses
Musculoskeletal Disorders
(MSDs)
Patient Transfer
Patient Lift

ABSTRACT

Nurses suffer a disproportionate risk for musculoskeletal injury compared to most other professions. Injury rates are far above the national average and may result in lost time from work, pain and suffering and is likely to shorten the working life of many nurses. Most nursing programs do not teach ergonomic principles and safe patient handling as part of the academic curriculum. The Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) tool was developed by ergonomists for use in the healthcare industry. This pilot study evaluated the risk for musculoskeletal injury during two lifts using REBA, one without a mechanical lift system and one with. Findings suggest that risk increased when using the mechanical lift system. We recommend evidence-based training for all nurses on patient transfer methods and use of all mechanical lift systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Work-related musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) are a major problem among hospital personnel, specifically the nursing staff (Gilchrist and Pokorna, 2021; Lin et al., 2020; Soylar and Ozer, 2018; Yasobant, 2014). The primary cause of musculoskeletal injuries (MSIs) in the healthcare workplace results from handling patients (Abedini et al., 2015; Soylar and Ozer, 2018). The overall workload includes frequent patient management including lifting, handling, and repositioning tasks that are required part of the primary services provided in nursing duties. Patient handling can lead to injuries to arm and shoulder strains and sprains, back and neck strains and sprains, and disc injuries (Lin et al., 2020; Soylar and Ozer, 2018; Vinstrup et al., 2020). The low back is the most or second most frequent site of injury (Gilchrist and Pokorna, 2021; Harcombe et al., 2014; Lee, Lee and Harrison, 2022). Nurses are involved in patient transfers from one location to another within the hospital daily and part of their usual job demands. Patients may be assisted in moving to and from their bed, commode, chair, and throughout the hospital for other services. Nurses are given the responsibilities for patient care and management, including lifting, loading, pushing, pulling, transferring, repositioning, and meeting patient needs (Soylar and Ozer, 2018). Nurses frequently encounter circumstances that necessitate assuming awkward postures and high forces that result in risk increases for MSIs (Lee, Lee and Harrison, 2022; Lin et al., 2020; Soylar and Ozer, 2018). The healthcare industry prioritizes the health and well-being of the patient over that of the providers. Despite no lift policies, individual providers tend to do “whatever it takes” to care for and handle

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patients, assisting them in moving from one position or location safely, even at the risk of injury to themselves.

In response to the patient-handling challenges, in the healthcare industry at large and many healthcare facilities have implemented specialized lift-assist systems and tools to aid nurses in effectively moving and handling patients with reduced risk for MSI (Santaguida et al., 2005; Ziam et al., 2020). There is a range of patient-handling equipment available depending on the needs of the nurses, patients, the hospital, the age of the facility, or patients at home. Regardless of the specific type of equipment, these tools were designed to reduce the stress and strain put on nurses, but they do require training on the proper use and maintenance (Santaguida et al., 2005; Ziam et al., 2020). A question arises among safety and health professionals; do these tools effectively reduce musculoskeletal stress to the provider and overall occurrence of MSI and resulting MSD?

Ergonomic assessment tools such as the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) were designed to address the challenges of evaluating healthcare workers involved in awkward postures while handling patient (Hignett and McAtamney, 2000). The REBA has been used for over two decades successfully to evaluate ergonomic risks associated with patient handling and management (Ayvaz et al., 2023; Raman, Ramlogan, Sweet and Sweet, 2020) and other industries (Hita-Gutiérrez et al., 2020). Janowitz and colleagues (2006) validated the REBA tool using medical personnel from a large cohort of approximately 6,000 workers in the San Francisco Bay area. The investigation evaluated 494 subjects and recorded 14,404 observations. They found good Kappa scores > 0.8 for low back, leg and static postures with decreasing scores for the remainder of variables evaluated. Inter-rater reliability Kappa scores were 0.54 for upper back and 0.66 for lower back. They concluded the tool was valid and useful for evaluating ergonomic risk in the hospital setting.

Another investigation team evaluated 383 nurses using REBA to estimate their risk for MSI (Ayvaz et al., 2023). The researchers found that 92% to 100% of nurses completing a variety of job tasks suffered musculoskeletal pain. Corresponding REBA scores ranged from a low of 5.5 to a high of 10. Researchers concluded that nurses were at medium risk for MSI and that ergonomic assessments should include a quantitative approach such as REBA (Ayvaz et al., 2023).

Another study looked at postures and stresses associated with dental student training. They evaluated 28 third-year dental students and found that the ergonomic assessment tool performed well (Ramam, Ramlogan, Sweet and Sweet, 2020). The inter-rater reliability was good, Kappa 0.625 with p-value < 0.01 and moderate concordance with Kendall's Tau-b of 0.58. The research team concluded that the tool was easy to use and moderately reliable (Ramam, Ramlogan, Sweet and Sweet, 2020).

The REBA ergonomic assessment tool was used in this study because of its appropriateness, history of development, and validity for use in the healthcare setting, see Appendix A. The REBA Excel spreadsheets are available as freeware from a number of sources including, The Ergonomics Center at North Carolina State University (<https://www.ergocenter.ncsu.edu/>) and at the University of South Florida, USF Health Ergonomics (<https://health.usf.edu/publichealth/tbernard/ergotools>).

This study investigated the ergonomic risk associated with patient transfers and a local healthcare facility in Southwest Montana, USA. The purpose of this study was to obtain REBA scores from nurses performing patient transfers and to compare scores with and without the use of lift assist devices.

1.1 Research Questions

- What level of risk for MSI do nurses encounter completing patient transfers without using equipment designed to assist in patient lifts?

- What level of risk for MSI do nurses encounter using the patient transfer equipment designed to assist in patient lifts?
- Will ergonomic assessments using REBA identify similar or different risk levels when using the patient transfer equipment?

1.2 Research MSIs and MSDs in Nursing

Nurses play a vital role within the healthcare industry and suffer a disproportionate burden of MSIs and MSDs (BLS, 2021). The US BLS reported that 44,020 nurses suffered injuries that resulted in 205,780 lost workdays in 2020. A research team investigated workers' compensation claims filed by nurses between 2007 – 2016 in California and found 199,547 cases (Lee, Lee and Harrison, 2022). The cohort included 51,189 nurses across the state. The most frequent body part was the upper extremity, followed by the low back, trunk, shoulder, lower extremities and neck (Lee, Lee and Harrison, 2022).

The typical nurse's job description requires them to perform physically demanding tasks including lifting heavy equipment and helping patients with their transportation needs such as repositioning in bed, moving from bed to a chair, from a chair to a toilet, and therefore back to bed (Soylar & Ozer, 2018; Lee, Lee and Harrison, 2022). Because patient transfer tasks are so physically stressful, many nursing personnel develop MSDs at some point in their career (Lin et al., 2020). The primary injuries are to the lower back, shoulders, and upper extremities (Lee, Lee and Harrison, 2022; Lin et al., 2020). Low back injuries and resulting pain remain the leading cause of early retirement (Goodwin, 2012). MSDs are prevalent between 33% to 88% within the healthcare industry and rank among the high-risk industries for low back disorders and other MSDs (Soylar & Ozer, 2018). These researchers found MSDs among nursing personnel were pervasive around the world and consistently highest in Estonia, Turkey, and Taiwan at 84%, 79.5%, and 76% respectively. Their review study looked at 34 published articles and found most commonly MSDs affected the shoulders, neck, lower back, and upper extremities (Soylar & Ozer, 2018). The researchers identified not only physical factors associated with MSDs but also demographic, organizational, and psychosocial factors that also played a significant role in MSIs leading to MSDs (Soylar & Ozer, 2018).

Paul (2012) completed a study to investigate the awareness among Indian nursing professionals about ergonomics, injury prevention, and safety measures in the workplace. This study also looked at the prevalence of MSDs among the population. Findings revealed that a relationship existed between musculoskeletal complaints and years of experience in nursing p -value < 0.05 . He found that with increasing years of experience, the probability of MSD-related complaints increased significantly (Paul, 2012). The cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Navi Mumbai hospital with 34 full-time nursing professionals (Paul, 2012). A questionnaire was administered covering the awareness of ergonomics in nursing, and safe work practices. All participants completed the Standardized Nordic Questionnaire to identify musculoskeletal injuries and health status including MSD symptoms. The findings from this study revealed 53% demonstrated a lack of awareness regarding ergonomics and safety measures related to MSI, also 75% of the population in this study did not use the proper recommended ergonomic techniques for patient management and assistance (Paul 2012). In addition, it was found that 53% of nurses complained about musculoskeletal injuries, and half of them reported pain in their lower back (Paul, 2012). The researcher found that nurses had poor patient handling techniques that contributed to musculoskeletal discomfort and risk for injury (Paul, 2012).

Another investigation aimed to evaluate the primary causes of lost time due to MSDs for occupations within healthcare (Ngan et al., 2010). The focus of this research was on measuring the relative risks (RR) for MSIs. Researchers found the highest RR of MSIs was among registered nurses and care aids

at RR 3.16 (2.38–4.18) and RR 3.76 (3.09–4.59) respectively. Comparatively, the BLS reported rates of time lost due to occupational injury were 8.8/100 full-time hospital workers and 13.5/100 for long-term healthcare workers, both rates far above the national average (Dressner and Kissinger, 2018). After the evaluation was complete, the research identified that MSIs were confirmed as the most common type of injury to healthcare workers, making up 83% of all injuries in the industry (Ngan, et al., 2010). These findings remain fairly constant across demographics such as age groups, gender, sub-sector healthcare workers, employment status, and occupation. The injury rates among nurses are higher than many work environments such as mining, construction, and agriculture. This staggering statistic causes us to empathize with the importance of addressing risks associated with MSIs and MSDs (Ngan et al., 2010).

1.3 Old Prevention and Training

Research also revealed that LPNs and CNAs are at highest risk for MSDs (Ngan et al., 2010). These findings indicate that more prevention efforts should be aimed at supporting the safety and health and wellbeing of healthcare workers who work directly with patients. Researchers advocated for programs to be developed and implemented to reduce risk factors and the incidence of MSIs within the healthcare community. They should be tailored toward each person's needs accordingly (Ngan et al., 2010).

A graduate thesis reviewed nursing programs and hospitals in Colorado regarding their education and the role ergonomics plays in MSI prevention for the healthcare industry and best practices (Goodwin, 2012). The thesis assessed musculoskeletal disorders specifically related to the manual handling of patients. The thesis shed light on the lack of training, and the importance of ergonomics training in the healthcare workplace. Without proper training, nurses will always be at higher risk of developing a musculoskeletal injury and MSD despite the tools and resources that were used (Goodwin, 2012).

Goodwin (2012) examined three traditional Bachelor of Science in Nursing programs, and four hospitals from two healthcare systems. A questionnaire was administered to all three facilities regarding the inclusion of evidenced-based training and education in ergonomics for nurses. The surveys revealed that each nursing school acknowledged MSIs are a major problem in the healthcare industry, especially related to patient handling (Goodwin, 2012). Although they recognized the issue, none of the nursing programs used evidence-based curricula to instruct nursing students on preventing MSIs, and ergonomic principles. Only one of the three healthcare systems surveyed reported that they had an established set of policies and procedures for educating nurses on the prevention of MSIs and MSDs when handling patients (Goodwin, 2012).

It was recommended that nursing programs incorporate evidence-based curricula within the program to ensure the delivery of a comprehensive plan for safe patient handling, thus minimizing nurses' exposure to hazardous risk factors and circumstances that ultimately can lead to developing an MSD. Hospitals should also implement a set of written policies and procedures as a part of their new hire process and assess regularly nurses' competencies through employment (Goodwin, 2012).

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

This research fulfilled the requirements of a Senior Project class at the university. The project proposal was approved by the primary faculty for the course. Participants in this study were recruited as a convenience sample from a local healthcare facility. The investigation included six female nurses between the ages of 28 and 48. All participants signed an informed consent form before participating in the pilot study. See Appendix B for the informed consent.

Participation was voluntary and subjects were told that they could opt out at any time. Lifts were simulated for the study and involved a volunteer rather than a real patient. Lifts were performed with and without lift assist equipment. A “Golvo” lift device or “Sara Steady” and “Gate Belt” are commonly used to aid nurses in a variety of patient lifts, contingent upon the desired destination.

The Sara Steady device provides a stabilized structure for the patient to pull on as they rise. This was used by the patient while the nurse assisted the patient to a standing position. The Golvo system requires the nurse secure the patient with a harness system and the device does the lifting. Each nurse performed both lifts, the first without lift assist, Sara Steady and Gate Belt only, and the second lift was accomplished using Golvo lift assist system. All lifts were video recorded for ergonomic analysis using REBA ergonomic assessment. The REBA Excel files were freeware obtained from the Center for Ergonomics at North Carolina State University: <https://www.ergocenter.ncsu.edu/>.

Ergonomic assessment risk scores were generated by observing the videotaped simulated patient transfers and completing the REBA worksheet. Each nurse performed two common lifts that nurses accomplish in their daily work. See Appendix A for REBA Evaluation Worksheet. The evaluator made observations and completed the providing input for each factor considered in the REBA evaluation. Key measures focused on postures and loading factors while performing the lift. The Excel spreadsheet generated the REBA scores or risk estimates. Data were analyzed using Minitab Statistical Software, Version 21TM. Mean scores were generated and the paired T-test was used to evaluate differences in mean scores.

3. RESULTS

All six nurses performed both lifts with scores seen in Table 1. The first lift, which consisted of a nurse using a Gate Belt and Sara Steady tool to assist the patient in transferring from a seated position to a standing position. Lift one had a range of 6 – 13 with a mean score of 8.3, see Table 1.

Table 1. REBA Scores for Six Lifts

Nurse	Lift 1- No Assist: REBA Score	Lift 2 – Assisted: REBA Score
1	7	10
2	6	10
3	8	9
4	8	10
5	13	9
6	8	10
Mean	8.33	9.67

No statistically significant difference, p-value 0.88

Figure 1 shows nurse 6 performing lift one. The nurse is lifting the patient using a Gate Belt while the patient is using the Sara Steady to rise to his feet requiring the nurse exert force to assist the patient to a standing position. The second lift consisted of harnessing the patient into a sling from a sitting position and transporting them to a bed using the Golvo lift device. The second lift doesn't require the nurse to lift assist but rather secure the patient in a harness system for a mechanical lift. The second lift had a REBA range of 9 to 10 with a mean score of 9.67.

Figure 1. Lift 1

Figure 2. Lift 2

When looking at the REBA Scores side-by-side, one can see that the majority of lift two scores are higher than lift 1 scores, see Figure 3.

Figure 3. REBA Scores for 6 Lifts - Lift 1 & 2
No statistically significant difference, p-value 0.88

4. DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

The results of this pilot study revealed there was an increase in the REBA risk scores using a no lift system. Both types of lift present risks for developing a musculoskeletal injury. Our REBA scores were consistent with prior research (Ayvaz et al., 2023). Nurses use lift-assist equipment when handling and transferring patients to reduce risks, our findings are contrary to expectations. The findings do not relate to initial expectations, as we anticipated lower REBA scores when using lift-assist equipment. While there was no statistical difference, p-value 0.88, we did not anticipate consistently higher values on lift two. The first style of lift revealed nurses are most at risk for developing a MSD in the shoulder

or upper extremity. The shoulder and upper extremity have been identified as common areas of the body to be injured in patient transfer (Lin et al., 2020). They rely mostly on shoulder strength from one side of their body during this lift to aid patients.

While the results indicated that there is still a considerable risk involved, the averages for lifting styles do not provide a complete representation of all the risk factors, more variables need to be considered such as experience, training, cycle time, number of lifts, and accurate force requirements for each type of transfer. The sample size was small and any inferences should not be made. Nurse six had a REBA score of 13, while the other nurses all had scores less than eight. This outlier may have significantly raised the average, making the lift look of higher risk than it was, and contributed to the lack of differences. Despite this change in patterns, it's important to acknowledge that the majority of nurses completed the patient transfer simulation with high levels of risk regardless of lifting styles. From this investigation, we learned that even with the implementation of tools and equipment to make the transfer safer, without proper training, the nurses can still be at a high risk for developing MSI and MSD.

The second lift had a mean REBA score of 9.67 and a very tight range of 9 to 10. The highest risk involved in this lift occurred when nurses bent down to wrap the harness around patients' legs. The most significant concern in this lift was the risk of injury to the lower back. This is consistent with prior research that identified the low back as the second most common body part injured (Lee, Lee and Harrison, 2022). Lifting the weight of a leg at the angle that feels most natural to these nurses poses a greater risk to their musculoskeletal health. As the risk was high with an able-bodied 150-pound male, this risk would be even greater for a bariatric patient.

Another factor that could have affected the transfer simulation was that some nurses participated toward the end of their shifts when they were fatigued from a full day's work. Thus, they may not have replicated their usual lifting protocols as when managing with actual patients. The recruitment of nurses for participation proved challenging, and those who did take part appeared somewhat rushed and exhausted.

Another factor to consider in the transfer simulation was a 150-pound 22-year-old able-bodied male was used as the false patient. He did not accurately represent the usual patient requiring a transfer. Nurses gauge how much assistance the patient can give them in their lifts, if the patient was a 200-pound person with limited mobility the results may have had a different outcome.

In the future, it is recommended to recruit a larger sample size that includes more nurses in the transfer simulation and collect more information on the nurses such as age, years of experience in their field, lifestyle factors, training history, health status, and any prior injury for a better understanding of the risks involved. It is also recommended to have nurses participate in transfer simulation at the beginning of their shifts when they are more energized and less fatigued and able to participate at higher energy level. It would be best to evaluate practicing nurses handling and transferring actual patients for a more accurate representation of what it is like to lift patients who are not able-bodied or overweight.

5. CONCLUSION

In summary, this research pilot project emphasizes the challenges that the healthcare industry face. MSIs and MSDs are prevalent and there exists an urgent need to develop effective strategies to mitigate ergonomic hazards associated with patient handling and transfer, this should be a top priority. Previous and current research confirms there is a high level of risk to nurses while performing patient lifts,

which should lead to further investigation and the implementation of effective controls (Lee, Lee and Harrison, 2022).

Based on this pilot research, one solution that could lower the risk is more in-depth training for nurses on the proper use of all lift assist devices used in their facilities. The tools may be effective at reducing risks to both nurse and patient, only if the nurses utilize them properly and safely. Training programs that teach the staff proper ergonomic techniques are essential to the success and well-being of the nurses (Goodwin, 2012). By implementing ergonomic solutions, there can be improvement in nurses's physical health, comfort, and productivity, as well as the safety of the patient.

REFERENCES

- Abedini, R., Choobineh, A., & Hasanzadeh, J. (2015). *Patient manual handling risk assessment among hospital nurses*. *Work*, 50(4), 669–675.
- Ayvaz, Ö., Özyıldırım, B. A., İşsever, H., Öztan, G., Atak, M., & Özel, S. (2023). Ergonomic risk assessment of working postures of nurses working in a medical faculty hospital with REBA and RULA methods. *Science Progress*, 106(4), 00368504231216540.
- BLS. (2021). Employer-reported workplace injuries and illness in-2020. Accessed 3/1/2024 https://www.bls.gov/news.release/archives/osh_11032021.htm
- Goodwin, C. I. (2012). *Musculoskeletal Injury Prevention Education for Nurses Provided by Northern Colorado Bachelors of Science Nursing Degree Programs and Hospitals*. Department of Environmental and Radiological Health Sciences.
- Dressner, M. A., & Kissinger, S. P. (2018). Occupational injuries and illnesses among registered nurses. *Monthly Lab. Rev.*, 141, 1.
- Gilchrist, A., & Pokorná, A. (2021). Prevalence of musculoskeletal low back pain among registered nurses: Results of an online survey. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 30(11-12), 1675-1683.
- Harcombe, H., Herbison, G. P., McBride, D., & Derrett, S. (2014). Musculoskeletal disorders among nurses compared with two other occupational groups. *Occupational medicine*, 64(8), 601-607.
- Hignett, S., & McAtamney, L. (2000). Rapid entire body assessment (REBA). *Applied ergonomics*, 31(2), 201-205.
- Hita-Gutiérrez, M., Gómez-Galán, M., Díaz-Pérez, M., & Callejón-Ferre, A. (2020). *An Overview of REBA Method Applications in the World*. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(8), 2635.
- Janowitz, I. L., Gillen, M., Ryan, G., Rempel, D., Trupin, L., Swig, L., ... & Blanc, P. D. (2006). Measuring the physical demands of work in hospital settings: design and implementation of an ergonomics assessment. *Applied ergonomics*, 37(5), 641-658.
- Lee, S. J., Lee, J. H., & Harrison, R. (2022). Safe patient handling legislation and musculoskeletal disorders among California healthcare workers: Analysis of workers' compensation data, 2007–2016. *American journal of industrial medicine*, 65(7), 589-603.
- Lin, S. C., Lin, L. L., Liu, C. J., Fang, C. K., & Lin, M. H. (2020). Exploring the factors affecting musculoskeletal disorders risk among hospital nurses. *PLoS One*, 15(4), e0231319.
- Ngan, K., Drebit, S., Siow, S., Yu, S., Keen, D., & Alamgir, H. (2010). *Risks and causes of musculoskeletal injuries among health care workers*. *Occupational Medicine*, 60(5), 389–394.
- Paul, A. (2012). A Pilot Study on Awareness of Ergonomics and Prevalence of Musculoskeletal Injuries among Nursing Professionals. *International Journal of Nursing Education*, 4(1).
- Raman, V., Ramlogan, S., Sweet, J., & Sweet, D. (2020). Application of the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) in assessing chairside ergonomic risk of dental students. *British dental journal*, 1-6.

Santaguida, P., Pierrynowski, M., Goldsmith, C., & Fernie, G. (2005). *Comparison of cumulative low back loads of caregivers when transferring patients using overhead and floor mechanical lifting devices*. *Clinical Biomechanics*, 20(9), 906–916

Soylar, P., & Ozer, A. (2018). Evaluation of the prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders in nurses: a systematic review. *Med Sci*, 7(3), 479-85.

Vinstrip, J., Jakobsen, M., Pascal, M., & Anderson, L. (2020). *Physical exposure during patient transfer and risk of back injury & low-back pain: prospective cohort study*. *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*, 21(1), N.PAG.

Yasobant, S. (2014). *Work-related musculoskeletal disorders among health care professionals: A cross-sectional assessment of risk factors in a tertiary hospital, India*. *Indian Journal of Occupational Environmental Medicine*, 18(2), 75–81.

Ziam, S., Laroche, E., Lakhali, S., Alderson, M., & Gagne, C. (2020). Application of MSD prevention practices by nursing staff working in healthcare settings. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics*, 77, 102959.

APPENDIX A: REBA Evaluation Worksheet

REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Permission granted by Dr Lynn McAnatomary to convert the paper based format to an Excel spreadsheet version.

A. Neck, Trunk and Leg Analysis

Step 1: Locate Neck Position

Step 1a Adjust....
If neck is twisted: +1
If neck is side bending: +1

Neck Score: 3

Step 2: Locate Trunk Position

Step 2a: Adjust....
If trunk is twisted: +1
If trunk is side bending: +1

Trunk Score: 4

Step 3: Legs

Leg Score: 3

Step 4: Look-up Posture Score in Table A
Using values from steps 1-3 above, locate score in Table A

Posture Score A: 8

Step 5: Add Force/Load Score
If Load < 5kgs: +0
If Load is 5 to 10kgs +1
If load >22lbs +2
Adjust: If shock or rapid build up of force: add +1

Force/Load Score: 2

Step 6: Score A, Find Row in Table C
Add values from steps 4 & 5 to obtain Score A. Find row in Table C.

Score A: 10

B: Arms and Wrist Analysis

Step 7: Locate Upper Arm Position:

Step 7a: Adjust....
If shoulder is raised: +1
If Upper Arm is abducted: +1
If arm is supported or leaning: -1

Upper Arm Score: 2

Step 8: Locate Lower Arm Position:

Lower Arm Score: 2

Step 9: Locate Wrist Position:

Step 9a: Adjust....
If wrist is bent from midline or twisted: Add +1

Wrist Score: 2

Step 10: Look-up Posture Score in Table B:
Using values from steps 7-9 above, locate score in Table B

Posture Score B: 3

Step 11: Add Coupling Score
Well fitted handles and mid range power grip: good: +0
Acceptable but not ideal hold or coupling: acceptable with another body part: fair: +1
Hand hold not acceptable but possible: poor: +2
No handles, awkward, unsafe with any body part. Unacceptable: +3

Coupling Score: +

Step 12: Score B, Find column in Table C
Add values from steps 10 & 11 to obtain Score B. Find Column in Table C and match with Score A in row from step 6 to obtain Table C score.

Score B: 4

Table A: Neck

		1				2				3			
Legs		1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Trunk Posture Score	1	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
	2	2	3	4	5	3	4	5	6	4	5	6	7
	3	2	4	5	6	4	5	6	7	5	6	7	8
	4	3	5	6	7	5	6	7	8	6	7	8	9
	5	4	6	7	8	6	7	8	9	7	8	9	9

Table B: Lower Arm

		1				2			
Wrist		1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Upper Arm Score	1	1	2	2	1	2	3	4	4
	2	1	2	3	2	3	4	5	5
	3	3	4	5	4	5	6	7	7
	4	4	5	6	5	6	7	8	8
	5	6	7	8	7	8	9	9	9

Table C: Score A (score from table A + load/force score) vs Score B (table B value + coupling score)

Score A	Score B											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	1	1	1	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	7	7
2	1	2	2	3	4	4	5	6	7	7	8	8
3	2	3	3	3	4	5	6	7	7	8	8	8
4	3	4	4	4	5	6	7	8	8	9	9	9
5	4	4	4	4	5	6	7	8	8	9	9	9
6	6	6	6	6	7	8	8	9	9	10	10	10
7	7	7	7	7	8	9	9	10	10	11	11	11
8	8	8	8	8	9	10	10	10	10	11	11	11
9	9	9	9	9	10	10	10	11	11	11	12	12
10	10	10	10	11	11	11	11	12	12	12	12	12
11	11	11	11	11	11	11	12	12	12	12	12	12
12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12

Final REBA Score: 13

Scoring:
1 = Negligible risk
2 or 3 = low risk, change may be needed
4 to 7 = medium risk, further investigation, change soon
8 to 10 = high risk, investigate & implement change
11+ = very high risk, implement change

APPENDIX B: Consent Form

Research Informed Consent

TITLE OF STUDY

Risk Assessment for Healthcare workers during patient transfers using REBA

PRIMARY RESEARCHER

Name Madelyn Mariegard
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PURPOSE OF STUDY

The objective of this research is to assess the risk involved in manually handling patients. The method that will be used to quantify risk of injuries is the REBA – Rapid Entire Body Assessment. This is an economic analysis tool that will analyze the level of risk involved that is associated with each specific task. This will also be accompanied by a short qualitative questionnaire.

PROCEDURES

In the initial phase of our study, we will administer a survey to six participating nurses. This survey consists of four questions, two of which pertain to the depth of their training received during their nursing education, while the remaining two focus on training prior to commencing employment. These inquiries are fundamental in establishing a comprehensive understanding of the participants' educational and professional backgrounds, thereby providing the necessary context for the subsequent simulation phase. Following the completion of the questionnaire, the participating nurses will partake in a simulated exercise. This simulation involves the execution of two patient lifts by each nurse. It is noteworthy that, for these simulations, we will employ a volunteer as the standardized patient. This approach is adopted to maintain a consistent factor throughout the simulations: the patient's characteristics. This consistency is imperative to isolate and scrutinize the impact of the nurses' training and experience on their performance in patient lifts.

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CONFIDENTIALITY

Please do not write any identifying information.

Every effort will be made by the researcher to preserve your confidentiality including the following:

- Assigning code names/numbers for participants that will be used on all research notes and documents
- Keeping notes, interview transcriptions, and any other identifying participant information in a locked file cabinet in the personal possession of the researcher.

Participant data will be kept confidential except in cases where the researcher is legally obligated to report specific incidents. These incidents include, but may not be limited to, incidents of abuse and suicide risk.

CONTACT INFORMATION

If you have questions at any time about this study, or you experience adverse effects as the result of participating in this study, you may contact the researcher whose contact information is provided on the first page. If you have questions regarding your rights as a research participant, or if problems arise which you do not feel you can discuss with the Primary Researcher directly by telephone at (406) 431 6204 or at the following email address (mmariegard@mttech.edu).

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this study is voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part in this study. If you decide to take part in this study, you will be asked to sign a consent form. After you sign the consent form, you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. Withdrawing from this study will not affect the relationship you have, if any, with the researcher. If you withdraw from the study before data collection is completed, your data will be returned to you or destroyed.

CONSENT

I have read and I understand the provided information and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and without cost. I understand that I will be given a copy of this consent form. I voluntarily agree to take part in this study.

Participant's Signature _____ Date _____

Researcher's Signature _____ Date _____

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MAIN AUTHOR

Madelyn Mariegard, BS, GSP is a recent graduate in Occupational, Safety and Health from Montana Technological University. She completed two internships during her studies, learning much about confined space safety, emergency action plan, SDSs, safety culture, construction hazards and safety training. She has joined Kellanova as their Environmental Safety and Health Specialist. Madlyn finds her work a great experience and is learning much. She will be working with a team to roll out a natural resource conservation program.

